

(fig., a). This indicates a short incubation period of 1 h can be recommended.

ARA of whole and cut plants incubated in darkness did not differ significantly. However, ARA of whole plants incubated in darkness was significantly lower (about 40%) than that of whole plants in light. It is more convenient to use cut plants in measuring ARA because they require smaller incubation vessels (plastic bags) and less acetylene-air

mixture than whole plants. Dark incubation also eliminates the need for extra light facilities.

ARA was highest between 1300 and 1600 h (fig. b), and at acetylene concentration of 10-15% (fig., c). A 4-h interval between sampling and assay significantly reduced ARA compared with a 1-h interval (fig., d). It seems important to process the plants (field sampling, washing, cutting, and sealing in plastic

bags, etc.) as quickly as possible. Four persons can sample and assay about 40 plants/h.

If an experiment involves ARA measurements on a large number of plants, it may be advisable to assay only half the desired number one day and half the following day: no significant difference in ARA was obtained from samples taken two consecutive days (fig., e). ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of leaf cutting for rice herbage on grain yield of deepwater rice

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Rice herbage could be very important in deepwater areas where natural pasture for grazing is minimal. We studied the effect of time and frequency of leaf cutting for herbage on grain yield of deepwater rice in 1987 wet season.

Dry seeds of Thai variety Pin Gaew 56 were broadcast at 120 kg/ha on plowed soil 25 May. Seedlings emerged 4 Jun.

Five treatments were arranged in randomized complete block design with four replications (see table). Rice leaves were cut at the collar of the last fully developed leaf, at different times.

Effect of leaf removal on herbage yield, grain yield, and yield components of Pin Gaew 56.^a Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1987 wet season.

Cutting time	Herbage (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield components				
			Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Fertility (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Plant height (cm)
No cutting	—	2.02 bc	127	91	79	26.6	237 a
40 DAE	0.7 c	2.13 abc	134	85	84	26.8	221 b
70 DAE	0.7 c	2.20 ab	135	85	77	26.5	223 b
100 DAE	1.0 b	2.24 a	143	92	82	27.1	223 b
40 + 100 DAE	1.4 a	1.94 c	126	83	81	26.5	217 b
CV (%)	11.0	6.30	25.5	15.0	6.9	8.4	6.9

^aIn a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Grain yield was significantly improved by leaf cutting 100 d after emergence (DE), and was not affected by leaf cutting at 40 and 70 DE nor by double cutting at 40 and 100 DE.

Herbage yield was highest with double cutting at 40 and 100 DE. Herbage

production in one cutting and grain yield were highest with cutting at 100 DE. Plant height was significantly reduced by leaf cutting. This might have contributed to increased panicle number, which improved yield. ■

Fertilizer management

Nitrogen substitution with *Sesbania rostrata* in rice production

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We studied the effect of *S. rostrata* incorporation on N economy of irrigated transplanted rice. Field experiments were conducted during 1987 and 1988 wet season in a factorial randomized block design with four replications. Soil was black clay loam with pH 7.8, 541.0 kg total N, 12.9 kg available P/ha, and 323.6

kg K/ha. Rice received varying N, 22 kg P, 41.5 kg K/ha.

S. rostrata was sown the last week of Jun and incorporated at 55 d old, 1 d before rice was transplanted. Total

biomass and N accumulation were determined at incorporation.

S. rostrata with higher plant density had the highest biomass production and N accumulation at incorporation (Table 1).

Table 1. Biomass and N accumulation in *S. rostrata*.

Sesbania population density	Biomass (t/ha)			N accumulation (kg/ha)		
	1987	1988	Pooled mean	1987	1988	Pooled mean
Low (333,000 plants/ha)	15.33	16.36	15.84	129.72	139.41	134.57
Medium (444,000 plants/ha)	18.07	19.07	18.57	151.49	160.73	156.11
High (666,000 plants/ha)	22.43	23.61	23.02	172.03	183.37	177.70
Mean	18.61	19.68	19.14	151.08	161.17	156.13
LSD (0.05)	0.41	0.51	0.34	15.24	11.74	11.17